

INCREASE FINANCIAL PRODUCT ATTRACTIVENESS IN FINANCIAL MARKETS

Samarkand Institute of Economics and Services
Ayubov Ilyas Ilkhovich, associate professor
of the Department of "Economic Theory"

Annotation: in this article, with the murak–cabalization of economic relations, an increase in the possibilities of redistribution of financial funds, derivatives allow not only to use new options for investing funds, but also to manage risks, which is most important from the point of view of reasonable investment the scientific novelty in this thesis consists in observing general development trends observed at the International and

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In the distribution of the right to ownership of the results of scientific and technical activities obtained at the expense of the state budget, the attachment of individual rights to ownership of such results to the state, it is not advisable to give their fate for officials to consider. A proposal to grant these rights free of charge to performers (except for inventions that apply to the havoc and defense of the country) seems more justified. It serves to increase the initiatives and responsibility of entrepreneurs in the innovative use of inventions and other results of scientific and technical activities. However, when introducing a new order, one should not forget about the third and main partner - the creative person who embodied his ideas in inventions and other results of scientific and technical activity. Scientists, constructors, engineers, other authors of new effective technical ideas and individuals who contribute to their implementation should receive a guaranteed share of the benefits and additional benefits that arise in this.

In a market economy, the process of redistribution of financial resources between economic entities is important, it is mandatory through the budget system and extra-budgetary funds, it can also be done voluntarily through the use of the financial market. For example, raising funds by issuing securities, placing credit contracts and loans. The receipt of funds, dividends, interest on the relevant assets by some economic entities and at the same time by other entities.

As an activity, financial transactions have an intangible form, that is, they cannot be touched as something and therefore cannot be sold at a fixed price. A financial transaction for sale must be carried out in the form of an item. The form of implementation of a financial transaction is instructions, rules, instructions, formulas, graphs, that is, a specific document. This document is a financial product that is the object of purchase and sale in the financial market. In financial markets, a financial product literally means something new. This new product manifests itself only in the process of selling it in the financial market or in the sale within the business entity. The buyer's demand for a financial product or operation determines the level of novelty of this type of novelty. If a new product that appears in the financial market is in demand and sold, then there are consumers of this product. The level of demand for a new product determines its level of utility and value.

Category of life in general and any economic, technical, biological and other phenomena. The business entity that came out first with its financial innovation and occupied its segment quickly creates an image for itself, and it is very difficult for the competitor to deal with it. The period of operation of financial innovations in the market is determined by its life cycle. The main features of the system elements of financial innovation are as follows:

- The system element performs only a specific function, which is not repeated by other elements of the system.
- The Element has the ability to interact with and integrate with other elements. This is a sign of a holistic system.
- The Element is closely related to other elements of its system.

A single financial product has a clearly defined range of its buyers. Therefore, it is produced precisely for consumers.

A bulk financial product is a product that does not have a clear individuality. It has no distinctive features. A bulk financial product is distinguished only by the type of product or financial asset. It includes all types of government domestic credit bonds, bank deposit account, pension policy, insurance certificate, option agreement, futures, etc.

Mass financial product is produced for investors and ordinary citizens. A new financial product will happen. A limited financial product is a strictly quota product, product size, or quantity. This volume is set when the product is released. The volume, quantity of production of products is determined by many factors. The size of the authorized capital of the business entity, the demand of buyers, is the presence of a unit of the product itself (Real Estate objects). Limited financial products include stocks, bonds, types of credit contracts, real estate facilities, and some other products. An unrestricted financial product is a product whose production volume (quantity) is not limited to any quotas. This product is produced for a potential buyer. The number of buyers is an uncertain value. Therefore, the volume of production of an unlimited financial product is calculated.

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